

Synthesis and Characterisation of Diethylthiocarbamate Complex of Palladium(II)

YANG RUINA, XI ZHENFENG and JIN DOUMAN*

Henan Institute of Chemistry, Zhengzhou 450003, Key Lab. of Coordination Chemistry, China

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Transition metals and dithio acid ligands such as dithiocarbamates, share a very rich chemistry¹. This report describes the preparation and characterisation of the palladium(II) diethylthiocarbamate complexes of the type PdCl.L.(C₂H₅)₂NCSS [L = Ph₂PCH₂CH₂PPh₂ (1), Ph₂PCH₂PPh₂ (2), *o*-H₂NC₆H₄NH₂ (3), *p*-H₂NC₆H₄NH₂ (4)].

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis data (Table 1) of the complexes correspond to the general formula, PdCl.L.(C₂H₅)₂NCSS [L = Ph₂PCH₂CH₂PPh₂ (1), Ph₂PCH₂PPh₂ (2), *o*-H₂NC₆H₄NH₂ (3), *p*-H₂NC₆H₄NH₂ (4)]. All the complexes are soluble in the specified solvents and stable in air. In all the complexes, thioamide band attributed from $\nu_{C=S}$ (1520 cm⁻¹) vibration does not show any change. This indicates no participation of C=S to Pd^{II} atom. The shifting of ν_{NH_2} band (3080 cm⁻¹) to lower frequency and splitting of δ_{NH_2} into two bands in the complexes 3 and 4 at 1600 and 1615 cm⁻¹, suggest bonding of NH₂ nitrogen to Pd^{II}. All the complexes show ν_{Pd-Cl} vibrations² at 310–320 cm⁻¹. Diethylthiocarbamate belongs to unidental coordination.

Thermograms show that the mode of decomposition of all the complexes are similar in nature. Gradual loss in weight at 150–650° is a common TG feature for all the complexes due to the oxidation of organic moiety. Quantitative estimation on the basis of TG curve also indicates the complete loss of ligand part (Table 1). Low molar conductances (5–9 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of all the complexes

indicate their non-electrolyte nature³. Thus, it is reasonable to propose square-planar structure to the complexes.

Experimental

Commercially available purest chemicals were used for the preparation of the complexes. Solvents were purified by distillation. The compounds PdCl₂.L were prepared by our reported method⁴ by the reaction of PdCl₂.(PhCN)₂ and L.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd no	Analysis %			Mol wt Found/(Calcd)	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	TG% Loss Found/(Calcd)
	C	H	N			
1	54.43	4.67	2.30	682	5.1	20.2
	(54.09)	(4.94)	(2.03)	(688.3)		(20.6)
2	53.01	4.96	2.40	670	6.3	22.1
	(53.43)	(4.74)	(2.08)	(674.3)		(21.1)
3	32.98	4.10	10.14	394	8.2	24.4
	(33.19)	(4.52)	(10.55)	(398.1)		(26.7)
4	33.30	4.61	10.62	393	9.0	25.0
	(33.19)	(4.52)	(10.55)	(398.1)		(26.7)

Synthesis of complexes: A suspension of PdCl₂.L (1 mmol) and sodium diethylthiocarbamate (1 mmol) in water (50 ml) was stirred for 5–8 h on a water-bath at 35–40° and then cooled to room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with water and dried under reduced pressure at room temperature (yield 85–94%). The complexes were recrystallised from methanol for further purification before analysis.

C, H and N were determined on an ERBA-1106

(Italy) instrument. Molar conductance was measured in acetone using $10^{-3}M$ solution. Ir spectra was recorded on a Nicolet 170SX spectrophotometer. Thermal analysis was made on a PE TGS-2 analyser. Molecular weight was determined on a CORONA-117 instrument.

References

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